

Portal founders recognized as science-wide top scientists by 2024 Stanford List

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“– So do you know which fishhook is the weirdest?
The whole class competes to describe their most bizarre fantasies...
Kingfisher the Wise shakes his head: – No! It’s a straight hook.

– In “The Weirdest Fishhook”; *Wild Wise Weird* (2024)

[SCIENCE NEWS]

Stanford University maintains a comprehensive database that highlights the world’s top 2% most-cited scientists across 22 fields and 176 subfields [1-3]. Developed by John P. A. Ioannidis and his colleagues in 2019, this essential resource assesses researchers’ impacts using various metrics, including citations, h-index, and a composite c-score. The database is periodically updated to ensure it reflects the latest metrics and rankings, with the most recent update occurring on September 17, 2024 [4].

In this recent update, we are proud to announce that two of the founders of the SM3D Portal, Vuong Quan Hoang and Nguyen Minh Hoang, have been recognized for their significant contributions to academia.

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August 2024 data-update for "Updated science-wide author databases of standardized citation indicators"

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Contributor: [John P.A. Ioannidis](#)

Description

Citation metrics are widely used and misused. We have created a publicly available database of top-cited scientists that provides standardized information on citations, h-index, co-authorship adjusted hm-index, citations to papers in different authorship positions and a composite indicator (c-score). Separate data are shown for career-long and, separately, for single recent year impact. Metrics with and without self-citations and ratio of citations to citing papers are given and data on retracted papers (based on Retraction Watch database) as well as citations to/from retracted papers have been added in the most recent iteration. Scientists are classified into 22 scientific fields and 174 sub-fields according to the standard Science-Matrix classification. Field- and subfield-specific percentiles are also provided for all scientists with at least 5 papers. Career-long data are updated to end-of-2023 and single recent year data pertain to citations received during calendar year 2023. The selection is based on the top 100,000 scientists by c-score (with and without self-citations) or a percentile rank of 2% or above in the sub-field. This version (7) is based on the August 1, 2024 snapshot from Scopus, updated to end of citation year 2023. This work uses Scopus data. Calculations were

Dataset metrics

Usage

Views:	3242113
Downloads:	822065

Mentions

Blog Mentions:	10
News Mentions:	250
References:	84

Social Media

Shares, Likes & Comments:	32869
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Figure: The database of 2024 science-wide top scientists, retrieved from <https://elsevier.digitalcommonsdata.com/datasets/btchxktzyw/7>

In the science-wise database, Vuong ranks 28,090th for career-long impact and 17,895th for single-year impact. Within the Social Sciences and Humanities—which comprises eight areas of study, including Communication and Textual Studies, Economics and Business, Historical Studies, Philosophy and Theology, Psychology and Cognitive Science, Public Health and Health Services, Social Sciences, and Visual and Performing Arts—he holds a rank of 5,197th for career-long impact and 16,511th for single-year impact.

As for Nguyen, 2024 is the first year that he has been recognized on the Stanford List. He ranks 306,049th in the science-wise database and 21,530th in the Social Sciences and Humanities for single-year impact.

Both Vuong and Nguyen have significantly advanced the philosophy of science through their development of innovative theories and concepts, including the mindsponge theory, cultural additivity, SM3D knowledge management framework, granular interactions thinking, and the informational entropy-based notion of value [5-7]. These foundational ideas underpin the SM3D Portal, and their global impact provides essential hope for its future growth and success.

Together, the portal founders represent substantial academic influence in their fields.

References

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